

Deliverable D6.1

Clustering Event Nr. 1

Funded by
the European Union

DELIVERABLE

Deliverable	D6.1 Clustering Event Nr. 1
Work Package	WP6 Maximising impacts and promoting multi-disciplinary ocean observing
Due Date	30 April 2025
Submission Date	29 April 2025
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Deliverable Lead	EuroGOOS
Authors	Inga Lips (info@eurogoos.eu)
Contributors and rapporteurs	Steffen M. Olsen, Justyna Bekier (DMI) Ronan McAdam (CMCC) Gerard McCarthy, Catherine O'Beirne (NUIM) Alicia Blanco (EuroGOOS) Deniz Karaca (EuroGOOS; BioEcoOcean) Florian Lüsrow (Uppsala University, BioEcoOcean) Nina Lepola (Uppsala University, BioEcoOcean) Said Hashim (Uppsala University, BioEcoOcean)
Reviewer	Chiara Bearzotti (DMI)

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1. Publishable summary

ObsSea4Clim aims to maximise impacts and promote multidisciplinary ocean observing. One way of doing this is by organising clustering events with similar projects and promoting multidisciplinary ocean observation. This deliverable is a report on the Clustering Event Nr. 1 held on 11-12 March 2025, in Sopot, Poland, organised with the sister project, [BioEcoOcean](#). Participants represented more than twenty relevant European and international initiatives and projects, such as BioGeoSea, [TipESM](#), [OCEAN ICE](#), among others. At the event, four sessions were organised to jointly discuss the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) concept and a joint contribution to their further development, their application to land-coast-ocean interactions and marine heatwaves. A last session focused on the key challenges in ocean observing.

2. Clustering Event I

Goal

The overall goal of the clustering event was to explain and understand the sister projects' approaches, find synergies in developing EOVs and indicators, and work towards better knowledge of land-ocean-coast interactions.

Structure

The event was structured into four thematic sessions:

- Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) speed dating: This interactive session facilitated exchanges among participants to discuss advancements, challenges, and collaborative opportunities related to specific EOVs. The format encouraged cross-disciplinary understanding and the formulation of partnerships aimed at refining observation methodologies and data utilisation.
- Bridging Land, Coastal, and Ocean Observing Systems – Integrating Physical, Biogeochemical, and Biological Data for Comprehensive Data Products: Addressing the continuum from terrestrial environments to the open ocean, this session explored methodologies for integrating observations across these domains, emphasising the importance of cohesive monitoring strategies that encompass land-sea interactions, which are vital for understanding nutrient fluxes, pollutant pathways, and sediment transport.
- MHWs in space and time: understanding thermal anomalies. Given the increasing frequency and impact of MHWs on marine ecosystems and coastal

communities, the session focused on identifying observation requirements, developing indicators, and understanding the implications of these extreme events on marine ecosystems.

- Identification of key challenges and barriers in ocean observing: This session aimed to pinpoint existing challenges in ocean observation systems, including technological limitations, data accessibility, and coordination gaps and to propose actionable solutions to overcome these barriers.

The clustering event was built on four brainstorming workshops, with the last one using the input from the first three to identify the gaps and challenges in integrating physical and biogeochemical observations/observing systems to improve the overall knowledge and assessment capability (e.g., provide input to the policymakers) and respond to broad societal needs (e.g., provide data and information products for the society). The recommendations developed during these sessions are instrumental in informing policymakers, guiding sustainable ocean management and enhancing the coherence of the global ocean observation and assessment community.

The clustering event marked a significant milestone for both projects, highlighting the key challenges that the ocean-observing community must address together. As the global community continues to push for an integrated ocean observing system, events like these are crucial in shaping the future of marine research and ensuring that we have the necessary tools to monitor, protect, and sustain our ocean.

Photo 1: The Clustering event participants. Photo: Dominik Krzyminski, IOPAN.

About the sister projects:

BioEcoOcean, Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem Ocean Observations.

Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136748>

This project aims to transform biological and ecosystem ocean observations through the development of the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science (BIOS), which supports and encourages operational workflows that adhere to the FAIR Data Principles. This innovative product promotes holistic thinking, facilitates communication, and strengthens the Ocean Observing Value Chain, designed to guide ocean observing programs at all stages—from planning to policy application—promoting a holistic and collaborative approach across the ocean observing value chain. The project engages stakeholders in co-creating BIOS to enhance communication and cooperation among various sectors involved in ocean observation and research. It also accelerates the implementation of biology and ecosystems EOVs to improve global biodiversity and ecosystem assessments while strengthening common approaches and standards through the development of standardised methodologies for observations. A key focus

of BioEcoOcean is to improve the understanding of the links between ocean biodiversity, biogeochemistry, and climate, utilising interdisciplinary approaches and advanced technologies. The project emphasises co-creation with stakeholders at local, regional, and global levels to ensure that its outcomes benefit policymakers, industry, civil society, and the scientific community. Furthermore, BioEcoOcean prioritises capacity building and collaboration with global ocean observation initiatives to promote widespread adoption of its co-produced standards.

ObsSea4Clim Ocean observations and indicators for climate and assessments

Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136548>

The primary objective of the project is to enhance sustained and multipurpose observations, which are crucial for meeting European and global climate requirements. By leveraging expertise across various domains, ObsSea4Clim aims to improve climate assessments, offer projections, and deliver actionable indicators for sustainable development. ObsSea4Clim has a strong focus on EOVs and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) and their use for the implementation of the Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR), as defined in the Manual on the WMO Integrated Global Observing System¹. The RRR process compiles information about requirements for observations, the capabilities of the observing system, and their cost-effectiveness, drawing on experts and impact studies to guide the most important priorities for addressing the gaps between requirements and capabilities. These efforts support both regional and global climate assessments, refine projections, and develop actionable indicators for sustainable development. The project seeks to create new ocean indicators that inform sustainable practices, advance Earth System Models (ESMs) by integrating EOVs and ECVs to reduce uncertainties in climate projections, and establish an interoperable data ecosystem that serves multidisciplinary needs across oceanic and climatic studies. Additionally, ObsSea4Clim prioritises the development of standardised methods for both in situ and satellite observations to ensure data consistency and reliability.

The work program is organised around four building blocks: the improvement of the EOV/ECV framework, the implementation of regional ocean indicators, the design of a nations' multi-purpose ocean observing integrating climate, services, and ocean health, and the integration of the designed system in European and global initiatives.

¹ <https://community.wmo.int/en/rolling-review-requirements-process-2023-version>

Both ObsSea4Clim and BioEcoOcean highlight the significance of collaborative efforts and standardised practices in ocean observation. By working across disciplines and engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders, projects contribute to enhancing climate resilience and promoting sustainable ocean management.

3. Sessions of the Clustering Event I

Session 1: Essential Ocean Variables speed dating

Session objective

The goal was to better understand the Physics, Climate, Biology, and Ecosystems EOVs and who does what with respect to each EOV under the clustered projects' spotlight. Since it was the first meeting of the two consortia, the idea was to familiarise themselves with the different EOVs and spark ideas on the challenges/possibilities of working on different EOVs.

Main Discussion Points

Overview of the main points from the session talks and discussions:

- Participants discussed the interconnectedness of EOVs across biology and physics, particularly focusing on variables like subsurface temperature and ocean colour.
- Several "polyamorous" relationships were identified, where one EOV, such as phytoplankton biomass, is linked to multiple other EOVs, such as ocean colour and sea surface temperature (SST).
- It was noted that it is essential to consider how living habitats can impact physical parameters, such as currents or temperature.
- Subsurface temperature was identified as a crucial parameter connecting many EOVs. It was found to be a key factor influencing other variables, like phytoplankton biomass, species composition, fish abundance, and benthic invertebrates.
- Sea ice coverage and light penetration (ocean colour), as indicators of albedo, can and should be measured in combination with phytoplankton and macroalgae biomass and coverage.
- A change in ocean colour may indicate a change in phytoplankton composition and, thus, in the "health" of the open-ocean primary producer population (also influenced by sub-surface temperature). This is then connected to a potentially increasing rate of downward flux of dying or dead phytoplankton, which feed the benthic invertebrates, such as filter feeders. Hence, a change in the water column could be linked to the biomass, presence or absence, and percentage coverage of benthic invertebrates.

Key challenges

Key challenges identified in relation to the session theme:

- Participants encountered difficulties understanding and integrating technical terms and acronyms across the EOVS sub-variables from different fields.
- Knowledge gaps were identified in how certain physical EOVS, such as ocean pressure, impact biological variables.
- It was recognised that there is a need for more explicit connections between EOVS, as they are currently developed in silos.
- The challenges of measuring certain EOVS, such as macroalgal biomass and cover, and the need to understand the habitats where species live in relation to physical parameters like currents and temperature were highlighted.
- It was noted that the scale mismatches between physical and biological variables need to be addressed, as different scales can lead to inconsistencies when integrating data.

Potential solutions

Potential solutions discussed during the session that could be taken to address the issues/challenges identified before:

- Involve a broader range of EOVS experts to provide comprehensive feedback on the EOVS specification sheets and consider sub-variables to cover all relevant biological, physical, and biogeochemical functions in the future.
- Foster interdisciplinary research that explores how variables like ocean pressure might affect biological EOVS through additional studies and model development.
- Develop integrated models that include biological and physical parameters (e.g., linking phytoplankton biomass to changes in Sea Surface Temperature (SST), currents, and sea ice cover to create cross-field data products that reduce uncertainties.
- Create integrated data products that combine satellite and in situ data to address scale mismatches between physical and biological variables, including statistical modelling.
- Consider the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools.

Next steps

The next steps/opportunities/plans identified during the session:

- Continue building connections between BioEco and Physics EOVs, particularly by focusing on phytoplankton biomass and ocean colour relationships, to develop data products that integrate these variables.
- Explore whether existing data products or models can be used to understand how subsurface temperature/current sea ice change/ocean colour changes influence biological EOVs or if new models need to be developed.
- Work on scaling down satellite data with in situ observations to bridge the gap between different scales and improve the integration of physical and biological variables.
- Organise follow-up workshops on practical data integration strategies between biological and physical EOVs.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Participants emphasised the need for closer integration between biology, ecosystem, and physics EOVs to enhance the accuracy of ocean observations and climate models.

EOV Data Compatibility: It needs to be assessed how data from different EOVs can complement each other, with a particular focus on aligning biological and physical data to develop more comprehensive monitoring frameworks.

Cross-Field Learning: The workshop highlighted the value of shared knowledge, with several groups identifying new opportunities to integrate biological and physical processes in climate impact studies.

Resources in open access available from this session

Nordlund, L. M., Lepola, N., & Olsen, S. (2025, April 25). EOV speed dating. BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim Clustering Event, Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282791>

Photo 2: EOVS "Speed Dating" session allowed the participants to identify what different EOVS have in common. Photo: Dominik Krzyminski, IOPAN.

Session 2: Land, coast and ocean interactions

Session objective

To explore the challenges and solutions for linking land, coastal, and ocean observing systems while integrating physical (e.g., temperature, currents), biogeochemical (e.g., nutrients, carbon, oxygen), and biological (e.g., plankton, fisheries, biodiversity) data. The session focused on leveraging EOVs and other standardised data types to create comprehensive, actionable data products that support ecosystem monitoring, climate adaptation measures, and sustainable management.

The session started with an introduction by Gerard McCarthy (ObsSea4Clim) on the need for integrated observing systems.

The core of the session consisted of three scientific presentations:

1. *Integrating Land and Coastal Systems: Linking Glacier Runoff and Atmospheric Inputs with Marine Data – An Arctic Case Study.* How land-based data on nutrient runoff and atmospheric inputs are linked with coastal biological data (e.g., benthic flora and fauna, plankton production, high-trophic-levels) and oceanic biogeochemical data. Speaker: Katarzyna Dragańska (BioEcoOcean).
2. *Coast to ocean data – Using EOVs to link physical (temperature, currents), biogeochemical (oxygen, carbon flux), and biological (species abundance, biodiversity) data across coastal and open-ocean systems.* Speaker: Toste Tanhua (BioGeoSea).
3. *Successful integration of biological data with physical and biogeochemical data – A case study of Irish aquaculture monitoring integrating with environmental variables (e.g., temperature) with biological data (e.g., organism health) for understanding and management.* Speaker: Gerard McCarthy (ObsSea4Clim).

The presentations were followed by a panel discussion with the three presenters, chaired by Karina von Schuckmann (ObsSea4Clim).

Main Discussion Points

Overview of the main points from the session talks and discussions:

- Talk 1: Speaker: Katarzyna Dragańska (BioEcoOcean):

- An increase in sea surface temperature (SST) can cause the melting of tidal glaciers. This can increase the amount of suspended matter in the water, potentially causing a regime shift.
- Retreating glaciers change the surface ocean properties (light, nutrients).
- Multiple EOVs are involved in the atmospheric (temperature, precipitation, wind speed), land (glacial discharge, geology, river discharge), and ocean (biological and physical processes, particulate) processes.
- Talk 2: Speaker: Toste Tanhua (BioGeoSea):
 - How EOVs are interconnected, moving ocean observations beyond an individual aspect (observational systems, programs) towards a connected global system.
 - EOVs are essential for an overall view of Ocean Health.
 - EOVs have varying spatial and temporal scales.
 - The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) in situ data can serve multiple purposes, including operational services, climate assessments, and evaluations of ocean health.
- Talk 3: Speaker: Gerard McCarthy (ObsSea4Clim):
 - Linking the fluctuations in temperature and the decline in the condition of Irish mussels.
 - Available data can be adapted, leading to increased innovation and the flow of data.
 - Expansion of the range of EOVs to biogeochemical and biological would greatly enhance this study.
 - Regionalisation of operational (satellite) products needs validation on small spatial scales.

Key challenges

Key challenges identified in relation to the session theme:

- There are issues with the time and spatial scales of the different data types.
- Satellite data must have high resolution, as cloud cover can be an issue when investigating plumes.
- Integration of differing data points is needed.
- Discontinuity of the data and the highly dynamic environment were noted.
- Coastal regions are harder to work with due to a lack of consistent data on a large scale.
- Inconsistent time scales and quality control exist.

- The EOVI indicator used by policymakers is not always straightforward.

Potential solutions

Potential solutions discussed during the session that could be taken to address the issues/challenges identified before:

- Use of machine learning with a drop camera to gather information in the water column for biological data.
- Use of drones to photograph plumes to get around the cloud cover issue.
- Development of interdisciplinary approaches and utilisation of open data format.
- Ensure that units and scales are in a universal format.
- Utilise AI if enough consistent data is available.
- Collaborate with local communities and industry to use any in situ data they collected.
- Facilitate the broader use of data collected for a specific purpose to increase the utilisation of available data.
- Communicate the skill of the scale of EOVI indicators for policymakers.
- Find out and communicate how indicators can be used to tailor solutions to stakeholder needs.

Next steps

The next steps/opportunities/plans identified during the session:

- Collaborate across various disciplines and engage with broad stakeholder groups.
- Identify the requirements, assess the available knowledge to respond to them, and determine if other indicators need to be monitored to meet the requirements.
- Expansion of the range of EOVI to biogeochemical and biological to enhance the study of Irish mussels.
- Regionalisation of operational (satellite) products needs validation on small spatial scales.

Resources in open access available from this session

- Draganska-Deja, K. (2025, April 24). Integrating land and coastal systems: Linking glacier runoff and atmospheric inputs with marine data – Arctic case studies. BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim Clustering Event, Institute of Oceanology Polish

Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15275398>

- Tanhua, T. (2025, April 25). Coast to open ocean data: Using the EOVS concept to link physical, BGC and bio/eco data. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15279725>

Session 3: Marine heatwaves

Session objective

The main objective was to bring together sets of partners working on different aspects of marine heatwaves (MHWs), in the hope of guiding each other's research and potentially finding areas for collaboration. In particular, a key desire from both projects was to discuss and develop a common understanding of which EOVS sub-variables need to be measured to understand MHWs and to measure the change in biology and ecosystems. Given the diversity in types and scales of impacts related to MHWs, the session also linked to the previous session on the issue of scales and regionalisation.

Main Discussion Points

Overview of the main points from the session talks and discussions:

- **Understanding thermal anomalies at ecologically relevant scales.** Works from ObsSea4Clim highlighted the longer-term (e.g. decadal) and regional-scale variability of MHW occurrence and characteristics, which helps determine their predictability and changes in time. Meanwhile, in BioEcoOcean, impact-based studies focused on the microclimates which exist in the ocean, and how, in specific environments, temperature changes are restricted to highly-localised areas (i.e. several metres across).
- **Defining and describing marine MHWs.** It became clear from the presentations and audience discussions that there is no consensus on the precise definition of MHWs (e.g. the minimum duration, the threshold used). When studying long-term variability, for example, two equally valid measures of threshold (i.e. fixed and moving climatologies) provide complementary information. A multi-definition approach is currently recommended when necessary.
- **Identifying the need for cross-project and stakeholder engagement to refine the indicator framework.** The learning experience was eye-opening for both projects, showing the need to consider all scales in order to produce user-relevant MHW information.

Key challenges

Key challenges identified in relation to the session theme:

- Agreeing on a definition of “extreme”. Are physics-based MHW statistics relevant to stakeholders?
- Providing information for a wide range of impacts, e.g. in coastal and offshore environments.
- Capturing the correct spatial scales - in “microclimates” when there are significant temperature differences on very small scales.
- Lack of data coverage in space and time in key areas, e.g. coastal waters.

Potential solutions

Potential solutions discussed during the session that could be taken to address the issues/challenges identified before:

- Optimise the use of the many tools and metrics available. This requires scientific studies, regionalisation, and broad stakeholder engagement.
- Collaborations and communication between sister projects BioGeoSea and BioEcoOcean, to promote multidisciplinary.
- Developing models that predict the capability of species to adapt to rapid changes in environments.
- Adoption of new tools: AI-driven forecasting for the local scale, network analysis to understand scales of MHWs, and new observational tools such as BioArgo to track phytoplankton abundance.

Next steps

The next steps/opportunities/plans identified during the session:

- Maintain contact between sister projects by organising common online and/or in-person events and workshops.
- Define compound extreme events (within all three sister projects), in order to identify the episodes with the greatest impact.
- Initiate stakeholder interactions to help focus the definitions used and scales studied.

Resources in open access available from this session

- Lehodey, P. (2025, April 25). Marine Heat Waves. BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim Clustering Event, Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282690>

- Joseph Kochuparampil, A., Surendran, S., Chatterjee, S., & P. Raj, R. (2025, April 25). Assessing the Frequency and the Intensity of Marine Heatwaves in the Barents Sea. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15279654>
- Haapaniemi, V., Siiriä, S.-M., Nummelin, A., & Haapala, J. (2025, April 25). Marine heatwaves in the Baltic Sea. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282851>
- Lüskow, F. (2025, April 25). The Blob and Pyrosomes. BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim Clustering Event, Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282616>
- Benedetti-Cecchi, L. (2025, April 25). Understanding marine heatwaves at relevant ecological scales. BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim Clustering Event, Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282547>

Session 4: Identification of challenges and barriers in the ocean observing system

Monitoring oceanic changes through EOVs is necessary to address pressing environmental challenges such as Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) variability, land-coast-ocean interactions, MHWs, and the development of ocean observation models and projections. This session examined the motivations, challenges, solutions, and policy actions required to enhance ocean monitoring systems.

Session objective

Identify the gaps and challenges in integrating physical and biogeochemical observations and observing systems to enhance overall knowledge and assessment capabilities, informing policymakers, and responding to broad societal needs through data and information products for society.

The discussions aimed to provide a platform for future collaboration and to inform common policy recommendations.

Main Discussion Points

Overview of the main topics from the session:

- Ocean productivity, including fisheries
- Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)
- Land, coast, and ocean interaction
- Marine Heat Waves
- Ocean observation models and projection.

Key challenges

Key challenges identified in relation to the session theme:

- Data scale and integration issues: EOVs are seldom measured across multiple spatial and temporal scales to provide a comprehensive understanding of ocean dynamics. However, there is a mismatch in the resolution of physical, biogeochemical and biological data, which makes integration difficult.

- Large-scale ocean observation systems, like the AMOC face challenges in aligning physical, biogeochemical, and biological data analyses and require synchronisation between datasets from different disciplines to ensure meaningful analyses.
- Data Availability and Validation
 - Models require the use of in situ data for validation; however, data collection remains limited.
 - There is an underutilization of available data, resulting in gaps in its application. Real-time and historical datasets should be integrated into ocean models to enhance the accuracy of projections.
 - Transparency in uncertainty reporting can also boost the credibility of ocean monitoring data.
 - There is a missing link between raw data and actionable information, which limits its usefulness for informed decision-making.
- Coordination and Collaboration Gaps
 - Lack of coordination at national, regional, and international levels affects data sharing and observation efforts.
 - Poor integration between land, coastal, and open-ocean observations creates knowledge gaps that impact decision-making.
 - Collaboration between disciplines (e.g., physical and biological sciences) is often limited, impacting holistic ocean monitoring.

The standardisation of data formats, the enhancement and improvement of real-time observation capabilities, and a strong, cohesive cross-border collaboration are critical for enhancing model accuracy and utility.

Potential solutions for improved ocean observations

Potential solutions discussed during the session that could be taken to address the issues/challenges identified before:

- Enhancing the data scale and integration solutions:
 - Enhance the spatial and temporal resolution of ocean observations by utilising multiple observation platforms, such as autonomous vehicles and satellites.
 - Equip Argo floats with additional sensors (e.g., cameras) to collect both physical and biological data.

- Implement downscaling approaches to make large-scale observations more applicable to regional and local needs.
- Enhancing data availability and validation:
 - Develop and deploy ocean health sensors and low-cost technology to expand in situ data collection.
 - Enhance data accessibility by adhering to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles.
 - Promote the use of citizen scientists, such as fishermen, to enhance biological data collection.
 - Use automated systems in ocean observation to improve data collection efficiency.
 - Ensure models are validated with real-time and historical in situ data to improve projections.
- Strengthening coordination and collaboration:
 - Enhance collaboration between scientists, private sector stakeholders, and policymakers to align data needs.
 - Establish better coordination mechanisms across national, regional, and global observation networks to prevent duplication of efforts and ensure effective collaboration.
 - Encourage co-design of observation systems by including modellers from the planning stage.
 - Enhance public awareness of tipping points in ocean systems, such as the AMOC, to inform policy decisions.
 - Incentivise the private sector's work on technological advancements to cater to the needs of communities and policymakers, contributing to climate resilience and sustainable ocean management.
 - Ensuring transparency in uncertainty reporting to enhance the credibility of data and models.

Next steps

The outputs of the session discussions will inform the development of policy recommendations, as planned in the ObsSea4Clim project.

- Support policies that prioritise developing and implementing science-based indicators to ensure consistent and reliable ocean observations.

- Advocate for the co-design of ocean climate indicators with stakeholders, ensuring that data collection aligns with the needs and priorities.
- Support the policies to enhance the uptake of FAIR and CARE principles and facilitate better coordination among various EOVS observations.
- Develop a standardised framework for documenting and communicating data uncertainty, enhancing transparency and supporting informed decision-making.

4. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following specific objectives of the project.

SO3	To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs
Clustering events helps us establish a European EOJ/ECVs network and promote multidisciplinary observing.	
SO5	To place Europe at the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus
Through this clustering event, we have gathered expertise on various topics that support evidence-based decision-making by providing an indicator framework focused on the ocean-climate nexus.	

Annex 1. Projects and initiatives represented at the Clustering Event

Project name	Description	Funder	Coordinator
Arctic PASSION	Co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system: the 'Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems - pan-AOSS'.	Horizon EU	ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR- UND MEERESFORSCHUNG
A-AAgora	Blueprint for Atlantic-Arctic Agora on cross-sectoral cooperation for restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems and increased climate resilience through transformative innovation.	Horizon EU and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO
BioGeoSea	Enhancing Biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables for European and Global Assessments.	Horizon EU	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL (GEOMAR)
Blue-Cloud 2026	Building on existing infrastructures like Copernicus and EMODnet, Blue-Cloud aims to create a federated ecosystem for FAIR and open data in marine research.	Horizon EU	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE

CLINT	The CLINT project draws on data collected by the Copernicus Climate Change Service. By applying an AI framework composed of machine learning techniques and algorithms, it will process large climate datasets to improve climate science in terms of detecting, understanding, and attributing extreme events.	Horizon EU	POLITECNICO DI MILANO
Copernicus Insitu TAC	The mission of the In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre (In Situ TAC) is to provide integrated and harmonised products built from in situ observations from multiplatforms and made available through the Copernicus Marine catalogue.	Copernicus	Part of Copernicus Marine Service
EFFECTIVE	Enhancing social well-being and economic prosperity by reinforcing the effectiveness of protection and restoration management in Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas.	Horizon EU	ASOCIACION CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO NAVAL Y DEL MAR
ESA PHYTO-CCI	The project will deliver products on phytoplankton diversity and carbon in the global oceans. Both metrics are essential climate variables that inform us about the	European Space Agency	PLYMOUTH MARINE LABS

	cycling of elements throughout the Earth system.		
Euro-Argo	This large research infrastructure provides an optimised and sustained European contribution to Argo by deploying 250 floats per year.	European infrastructure, different funding sources	Euro-Argo ERIC
EuroGO-SHIP	The EuroGO-SHIP project seeks to enable the European community conducting hydrographic observations at sea to provide higher quality and more sustainable data flows to a broad range of end users, more effectively.	Horizon EU	NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE
FOCCUS	Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users.	Horizon EU	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM HEREON GMBH
ILIAD	The ILIAD project creates an interoperable, data-intensive, and cost-effective Digital Twin of the Ocean.	Horizon EU	NETCOMPANY - INTRASOFT
LandSeaLot	LandSeaLot aims to integrate and enhance existing coastal observation efforts, including in situ, satellite, modelling, and citizen science, to better study the land-sea interface area, where	Horizon EU	STICHTING DELTARES

	terrestrial and marine habitats intersect.		
NAUTILOS	NAUTILOS aims to fill gaps in marine observation and modelling for essential ocean variables, including biogeochemical, biological, and deep ocean physics, as well as micro- and nano-plastics. This is achieved by developing a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, integrating them within observing platforms, and deploying them in large-scale demonstrations in European seas.	Horizon 2020	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE
NECCTON	NECCTON will enable the Copernicus Marine Service to better inform ocean policymakers, managers and publics about biodiversity conservation and fisheries management, using new modelling products for the green ocean: fish, pollution and benthic habitats.	Horizon EU and UKRI	MERCATOR OCEAN
NOCOS DT	The Nordic Cryosphere Digital Twin (NOCOS DT) project utilises digital twin technology in sea ice	The Nordic Council of Ministers	CSC IT Centre for Science

	research across the Nordic, Arctic, and Baltic regions.		
OCEAN ICE	OCEAN ICE assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on Planet Earth, via their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate.	Horizon EU and UKRI	DANMARKS METEOROLOGISKE INSTITUT
OLAMUR	OLAMUR aims to bring together multi-use low-trophic aquaculture (MU-LTA) related to key sectors, to demonstrate sustainable commercial solutions for both the North and the Baltic Sea.	Horizon EU	HAVFORSKNINGSINSTITUTTET
OptimESM	OptimESM develops a novel generation of Earth system models to deliver cutting-edge and policy-relevant knowledge around the consequences of global warming, including the risk of rapid change in key Earth system phenomena and regional impacts.	Horizon EU	SVERIGES METEOROLOGISKA OCH HYDROLOGISKA INSTITUT
POLARIN	POLARIN is an international network of polar research infrastructures and their services, aiming at addressing the	Horizon EU	ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM

	scientific challenges of the polar regions.		FUR POLAR- UND MEERESFORSCHUNG
SEAClim	SEAClim: European SEAs CLIMate impact prediction through regional models The SEAClim project offers detailed predictions of decadal to multidecadal changes in marine environments. Utilising advanced regional ocean models from the Copernicus Marine Service, the project will evaluate future changes in ocean circulation, waves, sea ice, and biogeochemical processes.	Horizon EU	MERCATOR OCEAN
SEARCULAR	By testing and refining four circular solutions to plastic waste, SEARCULAR is helping to support sustainable livelihoods and healthy marine ecosystems.	Horizon EU and UKRI	FUNDACION AZTI - AZTI FUNDAZIOA
SUBMERSE	The SUBMERSE project aims to develop a world-class research instrument by integrating existing infrastructures like NREN, EPOS, and the Copernicus Marine service.	Horizon EU	EUROPEAN FUTURE INNOVATION SYSTEM CENTRE

<p>TipESM</p>	<p>TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.</p>	<p>Horizon EU and UKRI</p>	<p>DANMARKS METEOROLOGISKE INSTITUT</p>
<p>TRICUSO</p>	<p>The TRICUSO project will advance sensing technologies on robotic floats and uncrewed vessels, supporting citizen science on yachts and improving data access for scientists.</p>	<p>Horizon EU</p>	<p>NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE</p>